

Decay of Temperature Fluctuations in Homogeneous Turbulence Before The Final Period For The Case of Multi-Point and Multi-Time in Presence of Dust Particles

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Abstract	Using Deisslers approach the decay of temperature fluctuations in homogeneous turbulence before the final period for the case of multi-point and multi-time in a rotating system in presence of dust particle is studied and have considered correlation between fluctuating quantities at two and three point. Two and three point correlation equations in a rotating system is obtained and the set of equations is made to determinate by neglecting the quadruple correlations in comparison to the second and third order correlations. The correlations are converted to spectral form by taking their Fourier transforms. Finally integrating the energy spectrum over all wave numbers, the energy decay law of temperature fluctuations in homogeneous turbulent before the final period for the case of multi-point and multi-time in a rotating system is obtained.
Keywords	Homogeneous Turbulent, Rotating System, Energy Spectrum, Temperature Fluctuations, Quadruple correlation, Fourier transforms, Multi-point and Multi-time.
Introduction	Knowledge of behavior of discrete particles in a turbulent flow is of great interest to many branches of technology, particularly if there is a substantial difference between the particles and the fluid. A dust particle in air, or in any other gas, has a much larger inertia than the equivalent volume of air and will not therefore participate readily in turbulent fluctuations. The relative motion of dust participate and the air will dissipate energy because of the drag between dust and air, and extract energy form turbulent intensity is reduced than the Reynolds stresses will be decreased and the force required to maintain a given flow rate will likewise be reduced.
Objective of study	In this paper we have studied the decay of temperature fluctuations in homogeneous turbulence before the final period for the case of multi-point and multi-time in presence of dust particle. The main purpose of this paper derive an equation for the energy decay law of temperature fluctuation in homogeneous turbulence before the final period for the case of multi-point and multi-time in presence of dust particle. When the frequency f is zero, i.e. for homogeneous turbulence of a clean fluid the result reduces to the one obtained earlier by Sarker and Islam (1997).
Review of Literature	Taylor (1921) pointed out that the equation of motion of turbulence relates the pressure gradient and the acceleration of the fluid particles and the mean square acceleration can be determined form the observation of the diffusion of marked fluid particles. The behavior of dust particles in a turbulent flow depends on the concentration of the particles and the size of the particles with respect to the scale of turbulent fluid. Saffman (1962) derived an equation that describes the motion of a fluid containing small dust particles, which is applicable to laminar flows as well as turbulent flow. Using the Saffman's equations Michael and Miller (1966) discussed the motion of dusty gas occupying the semi-infinite space above a rigid plane boundary. Sarker and Rahman (2000) considered dust particles on their won works. Sinha (1988) studied the effect of dust particles on the acceleration covariance of ordinary turbulence. Kishore and Sinha again studied the rate of change of vorticity covariance in dusty fluid turbulence. Deissler (1958) developed a theory for homogeneous turbulence, which was valid for times before the final period. Following Deissler's theory Loeffler and Deissler (1961) studied the decay of temperature fluctuations in homogeneous turbulence before the final period. In their study, they presented the theory, which is valid during the period for which the quadruple correlation terms are neglected compared to the second and third-order correlation terms. Using Deissler's same theory Kumar and Patel (1974) studied the first-order reactants in homogeneous turbulence before the final period for the case of multi-point and single-time. The problem was extended to the case of multi-point and multi-time concentration correlation by Kumar and Patel and also the numerical result of (1974) was carried out by Patel (1975). Following Desiler's approach Sarker and Islam (2001) studied the decay of MHD turbulence before the final period for the case of multi-

point and multi-time. Islam and Sarker also studied the first-order reactant in MHD turbulence before the final period of decay for the case of multi-point and multi-time. Sarker and Rahman (2001) studied the decay of temperature fluctuations in MHD turbulence before the final period. Sarker and Islam also studied the decay of temperature fluctuations in homogeneous turbulence before the final period for the case of multi-point and multi-time. They considered two and three point correlations and neglecting fourth and higher-order correlation terms compared to the second and third-order correlation terms.

Analysis

Correlation and Spectral Equation

For an incompressible fluid with constant properties and for negligible frictional heating, the energy equation may be written as

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial x_i} = \frac{k}{\rho C_p} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{T}}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} \tag{1.1}$$

where \tilde{T} and u_i are instantaneous values of temperature and velocity; k is thermal conductivity; ρ is fluid density; C_p is heat capacity at constant pressure; x_i is space co-ordinate; t is time and the repeated subscripts are summed from 1 to 3.

Breaking these instantaneous values into time average and fluctuating components as

$$\tilde{T} = \langle T \rangle + T' \text{ and } \tilde{u}_i = \langle u_i \rangle + u_i' \text{ allows equation (1.1) to be written as}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\langle T \rangle + T') + (\langle u_i \rangle + u_i') \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\langle T \rangle + T') = \gamma \frac{\partial^2 (\langle T \rangle + T')}{\partial x_i \partial x_i}$$

or,

$$\frac{\partial \langle T \rangle}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial T'}{\partial t} + \langle u_i \rangle \frac{\partial \langle T \rangle}{\partial x_i} + \langle u_i \rangle \frac{\partial T'}{\partial x_i} + u_i' \frac{\partial T'}{\partial x_i} = \gamma \left[\frac{\partial^2 T'}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} \right] \tag{1.2}$$

where $\gamma = \frac{k}{\rho C_p}$. From the condition of homogeneity it follows that $\frac{\partial \langle T \rangle}{\partial x_i} = 0$, and in addition the usual assumption is made that $\langle T' \rangle$ is independent of time and that $\langle u_i' \rangle = 0$. Thus equation (1.2) becomes

$$\frac{\partial T'}{\partial t} + u_i' \frac{\partial T'}{\partial x_i} = \left(\frac{\nu}{P_r} \right) \frac{\partial^2 T'}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} \tag{1.3}$$

where $P_r = \nu / \gamma$, Prandtl number; ν , kinematic viscosity.

Equation (1.3) is assumed to hold at the arbitrary point p . For the point p' the corresponding equation can be written as

$$\frac{\partial T'}{\partial t} + u_i' \frac{\partial T'}{\partial x_i} = \left(\frac{\nu}{P_r} \right) \frac{\partial^2 T'}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} \tag{1.4}$$

Multiplying equation (1.3) by T' , equation (1.4) by T and taking ensemble average, result in

$$\frac{\partial \langle TT' \rangle}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \langle TT' u_i' \rangle}{\partial x_i} = \left(\frac{\nu}{P_r} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle TT' \rangle}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} \tag{1.5}$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \langle TT' \rangle}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \langle TT' u_i' \rangle}{\partial x_i} = \left(\frac{\nu}{P_r} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle TT' \rangle}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} \tag{1.6}$$

with the continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial u_i'}{\partial x_i} = 0 \tag{1.7}$$

Angular bracket $\langle \dots \rangle$ is used to denote an ensemble average. Using the transformations

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial r_i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial r_i}, \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right)_i = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right)_{\Delta t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta t}, \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta t}$$

into equation (1.5) and (1.6), one obtains

$$\frac{\partial \langle TT' \rangle}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \langle u_i' TT' \rangle}{\partial r_i} (-\hat{r}, \Delta t, t + \Delta t) + \frac{\partial \langle TT' u_i' \rangle}{\partial r_i} (\hat{r}, \Delta t, t) = 2 \left(\frac{\nu}{P_r} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle TT' \rangle}{\partial r_i \partial r_i} \tag{1.8}$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \langle TT' \rangle}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \langle u_i TT' \rangle}{\partial r_i} (\hat{r}, \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = \left(\frac{\nu}{P_r} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle TT' \rangle}{\partial r_i \partial r_i} \tag{1.9}$$

It is convenient to write this equation in spectral form by use of the following three-dimensional Fourier transforms.

$$\langle TT'(\hat{r}, \Delta t, t) \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tau\tau'(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t) \exp\left[i\hat{i}(\hat{K} \cdot \hat{r})\right] d\hat{K}, \tag{1.10}$$

$$\langle u, TT'(\hat{r}, \Delta t, t) \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi_i \tau\tau'(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t) \exp\left[i\hat{i}(\hat{K} \cdot \hat{r})\right] d\hat{K}, \tag{1.11}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u_i TT'(\hat{r}, \Delta t, t) \rangle &= \langle u, TT'(-\hat{r}, -\Delta t, t + \Delta t) \rangle \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi_i \tau\tau'(-\hat{K}, -\Delta t, t + \Delta t) \exp\left[i\hat{i}(\hat{K} \cdot \hat{r})\right] d\hat{K}, \end{aligned} \tag{1.12}$$

(Interchange are made between the points p and p')

where \hat{K} is known as a wave number vector and magnitude of \hat{K} has the dimension 1/length and can be considered to be the reciprocal of an eddy size.

Substituting the equation (1.10) – (1.12) into equation (1.8) and (1.9) leads to the spectral equations.

$$\frac{\partial \langle \tau\tau' \rangle}{\partial t} + 2\left(\frac{v}{p_r}\right)k^2 \langle \tau\tau' \rangle = iK_i \left[\langle \phi_i \tau\tau'(K, \Delta t, t) \rangle - \langle \phi_i \tau\tau'(-\hat{K}, -\Delta t, t + \Delta t) \rangle \right], \tag{1.13}$$

$$\frac{\partial \langle \tau\tau' \rangle}{\partial \Delta t} + 2\left(\frac{v}{p_r}\right)k^2 = iK_i [\phi_i \tau\tau'(-\hat{K}, -\Delta t, t + \Delta t)] \tag{1.14}$$

In equations (1.13) – (1.14) the quantity $\tau\tau'(\hat{K})$ may be interpreted as a temperature fluctuation "energy" contribution of thermal eddies of size $1/k$. The time derivative of this "energy" as a function of the convective transfer to other wave numbers and the "dissipation" due to the action of the thermal conductivity. The term on the right hand side of equation (1.13) is also called transfer term while the second term on the left hand side is the "dissipation" term.

Three-Point, Three-Time Correlation and Spectral Equations

In order to obtain the three-point, three-time correlation and spectral equations, we write the Navier-Stokes equation for turbulent flow of dusty incompressible fluid at the point P, energy equations at the points p' and p''

separated by the vectors \hat{r} and \hat{r}''

$$\frac{\partial u_j}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (u_j u_i) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 u_j}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} + f(u_j - v_j), \tag{2.1}$$

$$\frac{\partial T'}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial T'}{\partial x_i} = \left(\frac{v}{\rho_r}\right) \frac{\partial^2 T'}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} \tag{2.2}$$

and

$$\frac{\partial T''}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial T''}{\partial x_i} = \left(\frac{v}{\rho_r}\right) \frac{\partial^2 T''}{\partial x_i \partial x_i}$$

Multiplying equations (2.1) – (2.3) by T'' , $u_j T''$ and $u_j T'$ respectively and then taking ensemble average, we obtained

$$\frac{\partial \langle u_j T' T'' \rangle}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \langle u_i T' T'' u_i \rangle}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \langle P T' T'' \rangle}{\partial x_i} + v \frac{\partial^2 \langle u_i T' T'' \rangle}{\partial x_i \partial x_i} + f(\langle u_j T' T'' \rangle - \langle v_j T' T'' \rangle), \tag{2.4}$$

$$\frac{\partial \langle T' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial t'} + \frac{\partial \langle u_i' T' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial x_i'} = \left(\frac{v}{P_r}\right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle T' u_i T'' \rangle}{\partial x_i' \partial x_i'} \tag{2.5}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \langle T'' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial t''} + \frac{\partial^2 \langle u_i'' T'' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial x_i''} = \left(\frac{v}{P_r}\right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle T'' u_i T'' \rangle}{\partial x_i'' \partial x_i''} \tag{2.6}$$

Using the transformations

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} = -\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial r_i'}\right), \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial r_i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i''} = \frac{\partial}{\partial r_i}$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\right)_{t',t''} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\right)_{\Delta t, \Delta t'} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta t'}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta t'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta t}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta t''} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta t'}$$

into equation (2.4) – (2.6), we have

$$\frac{\partial \langle u_j T' T'' \rangle}{\partial t} - \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial r_i'}\right) \langle u_j T' T'' u_i \rangle + \frac{\partial \langle u_i' T' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial r_i} + \frac{\partial \langle u_i'' T'' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial r_i}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r_j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial r_j'}\right) \langle P T' T'' \rangle + v \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial r_i'}\right)^2 \langle u_i T' T'' \rangle + \left(\frac{v}{P_r}\right) \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r_i \partial r_i} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r_i' \partial r_i'}\right) \langle u_i T' T'' \rangle$$

$$+ f(\langle u_j T' T'' \rangle - \langle v_j T' T'' \rangle), \tag{2.7}$$

$$\frac{\partial \langle u_j T' T'' \rangle}{\partial \Delta t} + \frac{\partial \langle u_i' T' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial r_i} = \left(\frac{v}{P_r}\right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle T' u_i T'' \rangle}{\partial r_i \partial r_i} \tag{2.8}$$

$$\frac{\partial \langle T' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial \Delta t'} + \frac{\partial \langle u_i' T'' u_j T'' \rangle}{\partial r_i'} = \left(\frac{v}{P_r}\right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle u_i T' T'' \rangle}{\partial r_i' \partial r_i'} \tag{2.9}$$

The six-dimensional furrier transforms for quantities in the equations (2.7) – (2.9) may be defined as

$$\langle u_j T' T'' \rangle \left(\hat{r}, \hat{r}', \Delta t, \Delta t', t\right) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left[\hat{i} \left(\hat{K}, \hat{r} + \hat{K}, \hat{r}' \right) \right] d \hat{K} d \hat{K}', \tag{2.10}$$

$$\langle u_i u_j T' T'' \rangle \left(\hat{r}, \hat{r}', \Delta t, \Delta t', t\right) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle \beta_i \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \exp \left[\hat{i} \left(\hat{K}, \hat{r} + \hat{K}, \hat{r}' \right) \right] d \hat{K} d \hat{K}', \tag{2.11}$$

$$\langle p T' T'' \rangle \left(\hat{r}, \hat{r}', \Delta t, \Delta t', t\right) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle \alpha \theta' \theta'' \rangle \exp \left[\hat{i} \left(\hat{K}, \hat{r} + \hat{K}, \hat{r}' \right) \right] d \hat{K} d \hat{K}' \tag{2.12}$$

Interchanging the points p' and p'' shows that

$$\langle u_j u_i' T' T'' \rangle \left(u_i u_i' T' T''\right) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle \beta_j \beta_i' \theta' \theta'' \rangle \exp \left[\hat{i} \left(\hat{K}, \hat{r} + \hat{K}, \hat{r}' \right) \right] d \hat{K} d \hat{K}' \tag{2.13}$$

$$\langle v_j T' T'' \rangle \left(\hat{r}, \hat{r}', \Delta t, \Delta t', t\right) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle \gamma_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \exp \left[\hat{i} \left(\hat{K}, \hat{r} + \hat{K}, \hat{r}' \right) \right] d \hat{K} d \hat{K}' \tag{2.14}$$

In these equations, \hat{K} and \hat{K}' are known as wave number vectors and $d\hat{K} = dK_1 dK_2 dK_3$. The quantities $\beta_i \theta' \theta''$ etc, are spectral tensors in wave number space corresponding to the correlation tensors in physical space. By use of these facts and equations (2.10) – (2.12), the equations (2.7) – (2.9) may be transformed as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle}{\partial t} & \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) + \frac{v}{P_r} \left[(1+p_r) k^2 + 2p_r k_i k'_i + (1+p_r) k'^2 - \frac{P_r f}{v} \right] \\ & \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) \\ = \frac{1}{\rho} i (k_j + k'_j) \langle \alpha \theta' \theta'' \rangle & - f \langle \gamma_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle + i (k_i + k'_i) \left[\langle \beta_i \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle - \right. \\ & \left. \langle \beta'_i \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \right] \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) \end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle}{\partial \Delta t} & \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) + \left(\frac{v}{P_r} \right) k^2 \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) = \\ & - i k_i \langle \beta'_i \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) \end{aligned} \tag{2.16}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle}{\partial \Delta t} & \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) + \left(\frac{v}{P_r} \right) k'^2 \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) = \\ & - i k'_i \langle \beta'_i \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) \end{aligned} \tag{2.17}$$

If the derivative with respect to x_j is taken of the momentum equation (2.1) for the point p, the equation multiplied by T'' and taken the ensemble average, the resulting equation is

$$\frac{\partial^2 \langle u_i u_j T' T'' \rangle}{\partial x_j \partial x_i} = - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 \langle p T' T'' \rangle}{\partial x_j \partial x_i} \tag{2.18}$$

Writing this equation in terms of the independent variables \hat{r} and \hat{r}'

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r_i \partial r_i} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r_i \partial r'_i} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r'_i \partial r_j} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r'_i \partial r'_j} \right] \langle u_i u_j T' T'' \rangle & = - \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r_j \partial r_j} \right. \\ & \left. + 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r_i \partial r'_j} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r_j \partial r'_i} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r'_j \partial r'_j} \right] \langle p T' T'' \rangle \end{aligned} \tag{2.19}$$

Taking the Fourier transforms of equation (2.19)

$$\langle \alpha \theta' \theta'' \rangle = \frac{-\rho (k_i k_j + k_i k'_j + k'_i k_j + k'_i k'_j) \langle \beta_i \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle}{k_j k_i + 2k_j k'_j + k'_i k'_j} \tag{2.20}$$

Equation (2.20) can be used to eliminate $\langle \alpha \theta' \theta'' \rangle$ from equation (2.15).
Solution for Times Before the Final Period

To obtain the equation for times before the final period of decay, the third-order correlation terms are neglected compared to the second-order terms. Analogously, it would be anticipated that for times before but sufficiently near to the final period the fourth-order correlation terms should be negligible in comparison with the third-order terms. If this assumption is made the equation (2.20) shows that the term $\langle \alpha \theta' \theta'' \rangle$ associated with the pressure fluctuations should also be neglected. Thus neglecting all the terms on the right hand side of equations (2.15) – (2.17), we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle}{\partial t} & \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) = \frac{v}{P_r} \left[(1+p_r) k^2 + 2p_r k_i k'_i - \frac{P_r f}{v} \right] \\ & \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}' \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

$$\frac{\partial \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K} \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right)}{\partial \Delta t} = \left(\frac{v}{P_r} \right) k^2 \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K} \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) = 0 \tag{3.2}$$

$$\frac{\partial \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K} \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right)}{\partial \Delta t} = \left(\frac{v}{P_r} \right) k'^2 \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K} \Delta t, \Delta t', t \right) = 0 \tag{3.3}$$

where $\langle \gamma_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle = R \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle$ and $1-R=S$ here R and S arbitrary constant.
 Inner multiplication of equation (3.1), (3.2) and (3.3) by k_j and integrating between t_0 and t we obtain

$$k_j \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle = f_r \exp \left\{ -\frac{v}{P_r} \left[(1+p_r)(k^2+k'^2) + 2p_r k k' \cos \theta - \frac{P_r}{v} f_s \right] (t-t_0) \right\}, \tag{3.4}$$

$$k_j \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle = g_j \exp \left(-\frac{v}{P_r} k^2 \Delta t \right) \tag{3.5}$$

and

$$k_j \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle = q_j \exp \left(-\frac{v}{P_r} k'^2 \Delta t' \right) \tag{3.6}$$

For these relations to be consistent, we have

$$k_j \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle > k_j \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle_0 \exp \left[-\frac{v}{P_r} \left\{ (1+p_r)(k^2+k'^2)(t-t_0) + k^2 \Delta t + k'^2 \Delta t' + 2p_r k k' \cos \theta (t-t_0) - \frac{P_r}{v} f_s (t-t_0) \right\} \right], \tag{3.7}$$

where θ is the angle between k and k' and $\langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle_0$ is the value of $\langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle$ at $t = t_0, \Delta t = \Delta t' = 0$. Letting

$\hat{r} = 0, \Delta t' = 0$ in the equation (2.10) and comparing the result with the equation (1.11) shows that

$$\langle k_j \phi_j \tau \tau' \left(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t \right) \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle k_j \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K}, \Delta t, 0, t \right) \rangle dK. \tag{3.8}$$

Substituting the equation (3.7) (3.8) into the equation (1.13) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \tau \tau' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t \right)}{\partial t} + 2 \frac{v}{P_r} k^2 \langle \tau \tau' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t \right) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} i k_j \left[\langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K} \Delta t, 0, t \right) - \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(-\hat{K}, -\hat{K}, \Delta t, 0, t \right) \right] \exp \left[-\frac{v}{P_r} \left\{ (1+p_r)(k^2+k'^2)(t-t_0) + k^2 \Delta t + k'^2 + 2p_r k k' (t-t_0) \cos \theta - \frac{P_r}{v} f_s (t-t_0) \right\} \right] d\hat{K}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

Now, $d\hat{K} (= dk_1 dk_2 dk_3)$ can be expressed in terms of k' and θ as $-2pk'^2 d(\cos \theta) d\hat{k}$ (cf. Deissler [1960]).

$$\text{Hence } d\hat{K} = -2pk'^2 (\cos \theta) dk'. \tag{3.9a}$$

Substitution of equation (3.9a) in equation (3.9) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \tau \tau' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t \right)}{\partial t} + 2 \frac{v}{P_r} k^2 \langle \tau \tau' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t \right) &= 2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} 2\pi i k_j \left[\langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle (k, k') - \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(-\hat{K}, \hat{K} \right) \right] k'^2 \left[\int_{-1}^1 \exp \left\{ -\frac{v}{P_r} \left[(1+p_r)(k^2+k'^2) + k^2 \Delta t + k'^2 \Delta t' + 2p_r k k' (t-t_0) \cos \theta - \frac{P_r}{v} f_s (t-t_0) \right] \right\} d(\cos \theta) \right] d\hat{k}, \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

In order to find the solution completely and following Loeffler and Dessiler (1958), we assume that

$$= ik_j \left[\langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \hat{K} \right) - \langle \beta_j \theta' \theta'' \rangle \left(-\hat{K}, K \right) \right]_0 = -\frac{\delta_0}{(2\pi)^2} (k^2 k'^4 - k^4 k'^2), \tag{3.11}$$

where δ_0 is a constant depending on the initial condition. The negative sign is placed in front δ_0 in order to make t transfer of energy from small to large wave numbers for positive value of δ_0 .

Substituting equation (3.11) into equation (3.10), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \tau \tau' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t \right) 2\pi + 2 \frac{v}{p_r} 2\pi k^2 \langle \tau \tau' \rangle \left(\hat{K}, \Delta t, t \right) &= -2\delta_0 \int_0^\infty (k^2 k'^4 - k^4 k'^2) k'^2, \\ \times \left[\int_{-1}^1 \exp \left\{ -\frac{v}{p_r} [(r+p_r)(k^2+k'^2)(t-t_0) + k^2 \Delta t + k'^2 + 2p_r k k' (t-t_0) \cos \theta \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - \frac{p_r}{v} f_s(t-t_0)] \right\} d(\cos \theta) \right] d\hat{k}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

Multiplying both sides of equation (3.12) by k^2 , we get

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial t} + 2 \frac{v}{p_r} k^2 E = w,$$

where $E = 2\pi k^2 \langle \tau \tau' \rangle$ is the energy spectrum function and w is the energy transfer term given by

$$\begin{aligned} w &= -2\delta_0 \int_0^\infty (k^2 k'^4 - k^4 k'^2) k^2 k'^2 \left[\int_{-1}^1 \exp \left\{ -\frac{v}{p_r} (1+p_r)(k^2+k'^2)(t-t_0) + k^2 \Delta t \right. \right. \\ &\left. \left. + 2p_r k k' (t-t_0) \cos \theta - \frac{p_r}{v} f_s(t-t_0) \right\} d(\cos \theta) \right] d\hat{k}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

Integrating equation (3.12) with respect to θ , we have

$$\begin{aligned} w &= -\frac{\delta_0}{v(t-t_0)} \int_0^\infty (k^3 k'^5 - k^5 k'^3) \left[\exp \left\{ -\frac{v}{p_r} [(1+p_r)(k^2+k'^2)(t-t_0) + k^2 \Delta t \right. \right. \\ &\left. \left. - 2p_r k k' (t-t_0) - \frac{p_r}{v} f_s(t-t_0)] \right\} dk' + \frac{\delta_0}{v(t-t_0)} \int_0^\infty (k^3 k'^5 - k^5 k'^3) \times \right. \\ &\left. \left[\exp \left\{ -\frac{v}{p_r} [(1+p_r)(k^2+k'^2)(t-t_0) + k^2 \Delta t + 2p_r k k' (t-t_0) - \frac{p_r}{v} f(t-t_0)] \right\} \right] d\hat{k} \end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

Again integrating equation (3.14) with respect to k' , we have

$$\begin{aligned} w &= -\frac{\delta_0 \sqrt{\pi} p_r^{5/2}}{4v^{3/2} (t-t_0)^{3/2} (1+p_r)^{5/2}} \exp \left\{ \frac{p_r}{v} f_s(t-t_0) \right\} \times \exp \left[\frac{-k^2 v (1+2p_r)}{p_r (1+p_r)} (t-t_0) + \right. \\ &\times \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r} \Delta t \left. \right] \left[\frac{15p_r k^4}{4v^2 (t-t_0)^2 (1+p_r)} + \left\{ \frac{5p_r^2}{(1+p_r)^2} - \frac{3}{2} \right\} \frac{k^6}{v(t-t_0)} + \left\{ \frac{p_r^3}{(1+p_r)^3} - \frac{p_r}{1+p_r} \right\} k^8 \right] \\ &- \frac{\delta_0 \sqrt{\pi} p_r^{5/2}}{4v^{3/2} (t-t_0 + \Delta t)^{3/2} (1+p_r)^{5/2}} \exp \left\{ \frac{p_r}{v} f_s(t-t_0) \right\} \times \exp \left[\frac{-k^2 v (1+2p_r)}{p_r (1+p_r)} (t-t_0) + \right. \\ &\times \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r} \Delta t \left. \right] \left[\frac{15p_r k^4}{4v^2 (t-t_0 + \Delta t)^2 (1+p_r)} + \left\{ \frac{5p_r^2}{(1+p_r)^2} - \frac{3}{2} \right\} \frac{k^6}{v(t-t_0 + \Delta t)} + \left\{ \frac{p_r^3}{(1+p_r)^3} - \frac{p_r}{1+p_r} \right\} k^8 \right] \end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

The series of equation (3.13) contains only even power of k and start with k^4 . The quantity w is the contribution to the energy transfer arising from consideration of the three-point correlation equation.

If we integrate equation (3.15) for $\Delta t=0$ over all wave numbers, we find that

$$\int_0^\infty w dk = 0 \tag{3.16}$$

which indicates that the expression for w satisfies the condition of continuity and homogeneity. Physically it was to be expected, since w is a measure of the energy transfer and the total energy transferred to all wave numbers must be zero.

The linear equation (3.12) can be solved to give

$$E = \exp\left[-\frac{2v}{p_r}k^2\left(t-t_0 + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right] \int w \exp\left[2\frac{v}{p_r}k^2\left(t-t_0 + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right] dt + J(k) \exp\left[-\frac{2v}{p_r}k^2\left(t-t_0 + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right], \tag{3.17}$$

$$J(k) = \frac{N_0 k^2}{\pi}$$

Where π is a constant of integration and can be obtained as by Corrsion (1958), (1960).

Substituting the values of w from (3.15) and $J(k)$ into the equation (3.17) and integrating with respect to t_0 we get

$$E = \frac{N_0 k^2}{\pi} \exp\left[-2\frac{v}{p_r}k^2\left(t-t_0 + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right] + \frac{\delta\sqrt{\pi p_r^{5/2}}}{4v^{3/2}(1+p_r)^{7/2}} \exp[fs(t-t_0)] \times \exp\left[\frac{-k^2 v(1+2p_r)}{p_r(1+p_r)}\left(t-t_0 + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r}\Delta t\right)\right] \times \left[\frac{3p_r k^4}{2v^2(t-t_0)^{5/2}} + \frac{p_r(7p_r-6)k^6}{3v(1+p_r)(t-t_0)^{3/2}}\right] - \frac{4(3p_r^2-2p_r+3)k^8}{3(1+p_r)^2(t-t_0)^{1/2}} + \frac{8\sqrt{v}(3p_r^2-2p_r+3)k^9}{3(1+p_r)^{5/2}p_r^{1/2}} F(\eta) + \frac{8\sqrt{\pi p_r^{5/2}}}{4v^{3/2}(1+p_r)^{7/2}} \times \exp[fs(t-t_0)] \times \exp\left[\frac{-vk^2(1+2p_r)}{p_r(1+p_r)}\left(t-t_0 + \frac{p_r}{1+2p_r}\Delta t\right)\right] \times \left[\frac{3p_r k^4}{2v^2(t-t_0\Delta t)^{5/2}} + \frac{p_r(7p_r-6)k^6}{3v(1+p_r)(t-t_0+\Delta t)^{3/2}} - \frac{4(3p_r^2-2p_r+3)k^8}{3(1+p_r)^2(t-t_0+\Delta t)^{1/2}} + \frac{8\sqrt{v}(3p_r^2-2p_r+3)k^9}{3(1+p_r)^{5/2}p_r^{1/2}} F(\eta)\right] \tag{3.18}$$

$$F(\eta) = e^{-\eta^2} \int_0^\eta e^{x^2} dx,$$

Where

$$\eta = k \sqrt{\frac{v(t-t_0)}{p_r(1+p_r)}} \quad \text{or} \quad \eta = k \sqrt{\frac{v(t-t_0+\Delta t)}{p_r(1+p_r)}}$$

By setting $\hat{r} = 0$ in equation (1.10) and use is made of the definition of E , the result is

$$\frac{\langle TT' \rangle}{2} = \frac{\langle T^2 \rangle}{2} = \int_0^1 E dk. \tag{3.19}$$

Substituting equation (3.18) into equation (3.19) and integrating with respect to k , gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\langle T^2 \rangle}{2} = & \frac{N_0 p_r^{3/2} \left(T + \frac{\Delta T}{2}\right)^{-3/2}}{8\sqrt{2\pi} v^{3/2}} + \frac{\pi \delta_0 p_r^6}{4v^6(1+p_r)(1+2p_r)^{5/2}} \exp[fs] \left[\frac{9}{16T^{5/2} \left(T + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r}\Delta t\right)^{5/2}} \right. \\ & + \frac{9}{16(T+\Delta T)^{5/2} \left(T + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r}\Delta t\right)^{5/2}} + \frac{5p_r(7p_r-6)}{16(1+2p_r)T^{3/2} \left(T + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r}\Delta t\right)^{7/2}} \\ & + \frac{5p_r(7p_r-t)}{16(1+2p_r)(t+\Delta t)^{3/2} \left(T + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r}\Delta t\right)^{7/2}} + \frac{35p_r(3p_r^2-2p_r+3)}{8(1+p_r)T^{1/2} \left(T + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r}\Delta t\right)^{9/2}} \\ & \left. + \frac{35p_r(3p_r^2-2p_r+3)}{8(1+p_r)T^{1/2} \left(T + \frac{p_r}{1+2p_r}\Delta t\right)^{9/2}} + \frac{8p_r(3p_r^2-2p_r+3)(1+2p_r)^{5/2}}{3.2^{23/2}(1+p_r)^{11/2}} \right] \\ & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1,3,5,\dots,(2n+9)}{n!(2n+1)2^{2n}(1+p_r)} \times \left\{ \frac{T^{(2n-1)/2}}{(T+\Delta T/2)^{(2n+1)/2}} + \frac{(T+\Delta T)^{(2n+1)/2}}{(T+\Delta T/2)^{(2n+1)/2}} \right\}, \tag{3.20} \end{aligned}$$

where $T = t - t_0$.

Equation (3.20) is the decay law of temperature energy fluctuations in homogeneous turbulence before the final period for the case of multi-point and multi-time in presence of dust particles.

Conclusion

In equation (3.20) we obtained the decay law of temperature fluctuations in homogeneous turbulence before the final period in presence of dust particle by neglecting the quadruple correlation terms in comparison with the third-order correlation terms for the case of multi-point and multi-time. If the fluid is clean then $f=0$, the equation (3.20) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\langle T^2 \rangle}{2} &= \frac{N_0 p_r^{3/2} \left(T + \frac{\Delta T}{2} \right)^{-3/2}}{8v^{3/2} \sqrt{2\pi}} + \frac{\pi \delta_0 p_r^6}{4v^6 (1+p_r)(1+2p_r)^{5/2}} \times \left[\frac{9}{16T^{5/2} \left(T + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r} \Delta T \right)^{5/2}} \right. \\
 &+ \frac{9}{16(T)^{5/2} \left(T + \frac{p_r}{1+2p_r} \Delta T \right)^{5/2}} + \frac{5p_r (7p_r - 6)}{16(1+2p_r) T^{3/2} \left(T + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r} \Delta T \right)^{7/2}} \\
 &+ \frac{5p_r (7p_r - 6)}{16(1+2p_r)(T + \Delta T)^{3/2} \left(T + \frac{p_r}{1+2p_r} \Delta T \right)^{7/2}} + \frac{35p_r (3p_r^2 - 2p_r + 3)}{8(1+2p_r) T^{1/2} \left(T + \frac{1+p_r}{1+2p_r} \Delta T \right)^{9/2}} \\
 &+ \frac{35p_r (3p_r^2 - 2p_r + 3)}{8(1+2p_r)(T + \Delta T)^{1/2} \left(T + \frac{p_r}{1+2p_r} \Delta T \right)^{9/2}} + \frac{8p_r (3p_r^2 - 2p_r + 3)(1+2p_r)^{5/2}}{3.2^{23/2} (1+p_r)^{11/2}} \\
 &\left. \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1,3,5,\dots,(2n+9)}{n!(2n+1)2^{2n}(1+p_r)} \times \left\{ \frac{T^{(2n-1)/2}}{(T + \Delta T/2)^{(2n+1)/2}} + \frac{(T + \Delta T)^{(2n+1)/2}}{(T + \Delta T/2)^{(2n+1)/2}} \right\} \right], \tag{4.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

which was obtained by Sarker and Islam (2001).

If we put $\Delta T = 0$, we can easily find out

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\langle T^2 \rangle}{2} &= \frac{N_0 p_r^{3/2} T^{3/2}}{8\sqrt{2\pi} v^{3/2}} + \frac{\pi \delta_0 p_r^6 T^5}{4v^6 (1+p_r)(1+2p_r)^{5/2}} \times \left[\frac{9}{16} + \frac{5 p_r (7p_r - 6)}{16 (1+2p_r)} + \frac{35}{8} \right. \\
 &\times \frac{p_r (3p_r^2 - 2p_r + 3)}{(1+2p_r)^2} \left. \right] = AT^{-3/2} + BT^{-5} = A(t-t_0)^{-3/2} + B(t-t_0)^{-5}, \tag{4.2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$A = \frac{N_0 p_r^{3/2}}{8\sqrt{2\pi} v^{3/2}} \text{ and,}$$

where,

$$B = \frac{\pi \delta_0 p_r^6}{2v^6 (1+p_r)(1+2p_r)^{5/2}} \times \left[\frac{9}{16} + \frac{5 p_r (p_r - 6)}{16 (1+2p_r)} + \frac{35 p_r (3p_r^2 - 2p_r + 3)}{8 (1+2p_r)^2} + \dots \right].$$

which was obtained earlier by Loeffler and Deissler (1961).

This study that the effect of dust particle in homogeneous turbulence the temperature energy fluctuations, decays more rapidly than the energy for clean fluid for times before the final period.

If the higher order correlation equations were considered in the analysis it appears that more terms of higher power of time would be added to the equation (3.20). For large times, the second term in the equation becomes negligible leaving the -3/2 power decay law for the final period.

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